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● Review of the genus *Tambana* Moore, 1882 (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae, Pantheinae) from Southeast Xizang

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Abstract: This study documents six species of the genus *Tambana* Moore, 1882 from southeastern Xizang, China. Among these species, *T. albiplaga* (Warren, 1912) is recorded from China for the first time and represents a new national record. *T. entoxantha* (Hampson, 1894), *T. subflava* (Wileman, 1911) and *T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998 are recorded from Xizang for the first time and constitute new provincial records. *T. indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015 and *T. variegata* Moore, 1882 are previously known from Xizang. Morphological descriptions are provided for the adults of all six species, as well as for their genitalia. High-resolution color images of the adults and genitalia are presented, supplemented with updated information on the species' distribution both within China and worldwide.

Keywords: genitalia, newly recorded species, *Tambana*, taxonomy

● 藏东南异后夜蛾属（鳞翅目，夜蛾科，毛夜蛾亚科）记述

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摘要: 本文记述了采自藏东南地区的异后夜蛾属 *Tambana* Moore, 1882 的六个物种, 其中包括 1 个中国新记录种: *T. albiplaga* (Warren, 1912); 3 个西藏新记录种: 内黄后夜蛾 *T. entoxantha* (Hampson, 1894)、黄异后夜蛾 *T. subflava* (Wileman, 1911) 和 *T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998; 以及 2 个西藏已知种: *T. indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015 和异后夜蛾 *T. variegata* Moore, 1882。本文对这六种成虫及其外生殖器的形态特征进行了详细描述, 提供了成虫及其外生殖器的清晰彩色图片, 并整理了国内外分布情况。

关键词: 外生殖器, 新记录种, 异后夜蛾属, 分类学

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● Introduction

The genus *Tambana* was established by Moore in 1882, with *Tambana variegata* as the type species. However, its taxonomic status has long been uncertain. Poole (1989), Chen (1982, 1999) and Hua (2005) treated *Tambana* as a synonym of the genus *Trisuloides* Butler, 1881. Speidel & Kononenko (1998) restored the generic status of *Tambana* and included 15 species in it, among which three are new and eight are new combinations. Subsequently, Kononenko (2004) described 2 new species of *Tambana* from southeastern and central China and reported *T. arctoides* as a new record for China. Behounek *et al.* (2015) revised *Tambana*, increased the number of known species to 26 (one unrecognized, including one subspecies) mainly distributed in montane forests at the altitude between 900–2400 m in Southwest China and Indochina Peninsula. In China, 17 species of the genus *Tambana* have been recorded (Behounek *et al.* 2015), covering a distribution from SE, E China to SW and W China. In Xizang Autonomous Region, three species have been recorded (Chen 1991, 1999). In this paper, six species of *Tambana* Moore, 1882 are described and a species-specific key is provided. Additionally, an updated checklist of the known species of the genus *Tambana* is presented.

● Material and Methods

Specimens were collected from various locations in Linzhi City, Xizang, during July to September of 2013–2023. On each survey day, a 450 W high-pressure mercury lamp trapping system was set up from 21:00 p. m. to 01:00 a.m. A killing jar was prepared using a 25% ammonia water solution.

Adult photographs were taken using a Canon 5DIV camera, while genitalia photographs were captured with a Leica S9i microscope. All images were processed using Adobe Photoshop 2023. The terminology for the morphology of adults and genitalia follows the works of Behounek *et al.* (2015).

Checklist of the genus *Tambana*

- T. albiplaga* (Warren, 1912)
- T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998
- T. bella* (Mell, 1935)
 - = *chekiana* (Draudt, 1937)
 - = *quadrata* (Berio, 1973)
- T. burmana* (Berio, 1973)
- T. naumanni* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998
- T. plumbea* (Butler, 1881)
 - = *ripleyi* (Holland, 1889)
- T. subflava* (Wileman, 1911)
 - = *albitessellata* (Hampson, 1913)
- T. tibetica* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
- T. succincta* Berio, 1973
- T. variegata* Moore, 1882
- T. entoxantha* (Hampson, 1894)
 - = *klapperichii* (Mell, 1958)
- T. c-album* (Leech, 1900)
- T. similina* Kononenko, 2004
- T. nekrasovi* Kononenko, 2004

- T. xilinga* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. mekongga Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. helmuti Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. fansipana Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. funebris (Berio, 1973)
 = *gerryi* (Thöny, 1996)
T. ronnyi (Thöny, 1996)
T. laura Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. glauca (Hampson, 1898)
 = *behouneki* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998
T. indeterminata Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. annamica Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015
T. annamica stumpfi Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015

Key to the species of genus *Tambana* from Xizang

1. Antennae of male moth bipectinate.....*T. albiplaga*
 Antennae of male moth filiform..... 2
2. Hindwing predominantly blackish-brown..... 3
 Hindwing predominantly yellow..... 4
3. White spot outside reniform stigma present..... *T. indeterminata*
 White spot outside reniform stigma absent *T. entoxantha*
4. Wedge-shaped stria with an acute angle *T. subflava*
 Wedge-shaped stria absent..... 5
5. Cornuti long spiniform..... *T. arctoides*
 Cornuti short spiniform..... *T. variegata*

● Taxonomy

Tambana albiplaga (Warren, 1912) (Newly recorded for China)

Tambana albiplaga Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015, Zootaxa 4048 (3): 305, 304(list). TL: India, Meghalaya, Khasis.

Material examined: 4♀, 80K, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 19-V-2019, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♀, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 25-VII-2015, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♀, Hanmi Township, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 18-VII-2021, leg. Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. *T. albiplaga* relatively large in size, Antennae of male adults bipectinate, those of female adults filiform. Forewing pattern dissimilar to other species of *Tambana*, with a large white spot between the reniform stigma and the postmedial line, the postmedial line distinctly whitish and curved in an arc. Hindwing with a broad blackish-brown band presented at the outer margin. Female genitalia Corpus bursae membranous, anterior part narrow and elongate, posterior part rounded.

Description. Female adult (Fig. 1). Forewing length 63–73 mm. Head dark yellowish-brown. Antennae linear. Labial palpi short, black and yellowish, apically black. Thorax yellowish-brown dorsally and yellow ventrally. Abdomen blackish-gray, both sides with yellow scales. Forewing ground color blackish-brown, irregularly covered with black and white spots. Basal line short, white. Antemedial line black, curved outwards, and tinged with white interiorly. Orbicular and reniform stigma brown and outlined with black. An irregular white patch presented between reniform stigma and postmedial line. Postmedial line white and protruded outwards at M₂. Submarginal

line black, triangular black stripes presented between postmedial and submarginal lines. An obscure white short line presented in subapical area. Marginal line composed of a row of disconnected black crescent-shaped patches. Cilia brown. Hindwing yellow, with a broad blackish-brown band presented at the outer margin. Cilia brown.

Female genitalia (Fig. 20). Papillae anales trapezoid. Apophyses anterioris about 2/3 the length of apophyses posterioris, both sclerotized. Ductus bursae short, with a funnel-shaped antrum and a short membranous anterior section. Corpus bursae strongly elongated and membranous, with an oval posterior section and a tubular anterior section.

Distribution. China (Xizang); India; Vietnam; Thailand.

***Tambana entoxantha* (Hampson, 1894) (Newly recorded for Xizang)**

Tambana entoxantha Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015, Zootaxa 4048 (3): 313,305(list). TL: India, Sikkim, Himachal Pradesh, Simla.

Material examined: 2♂, Hanmi Township, Médog, Linzhi, XZ, 29-VI-2021, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♂, Hanmi Township, Médog, Linzhi, XZ, 18-19-VII-2021, leg. Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. *T. entoxantha* small in size, the forewing with three consecutive white spots on the inner margin at the inner line, postmedial line, and anal angle areas. Hindwing from base to inner margin yellow, remaining large area blackish-brown. Valvae thick, with costa curved in a wavy manner. with a strongly hook-shaped harpe at apex of valvae. Aedeagus slender and cylindrical, with carina plate bearing short spiniform protuberances.

Description. Male adult (Fig. 2). Forewing length 41–43 mm. Head yellowish-white. Antennae filiform. Labial palpi short, black and dull yellow. Thorax yellowish-brown dorsally and yellow ventrally. Abdomen blackish-gray, both sides with orange-yellow scale. Anal tuft blackish-brown. Forewings ground color blackish-brown, scattered with pale blue-gray scales. Basal line yellowish-white. Antemedial line brown, curved inwards, and tinged with white interiorly. Orbicular and reniform stigma yellowish-brown and outlined with dark brown. Reniform stigmata with small white spots at both ends. Medial line a broad dark brown band. Postmedial line black, wavy and curved. Submarginal line brown, serrated and curved, both sides reddish-brown, inner side darker. Inner margin area yellowish-brown, with two smaller patches at antemedial and postmedial lines, anal angle patch larger. Cilia blackish-brown. Hindwing from base to inner margin yellow, remaining large area blackish-brown. Cilia alternating blackish-brown and yellow.

Male genitalia (Figs 10, 11). Uncus short and thick, blunt apically. Tegumen broad without protrusion. Juxta shield-shaped. Saccus long. Valvae thick, curved and lamellate. Costa protruded medially with a strongly hook-shaped harpe presented at apex of valvae. Aedeagus relatively slender and cylindrical, with the carina plate bearing short spiniform protuberances. Vesica saccate without any sclerotization.

Distribution. China (Xizang, Jiangxi, Fujian, Hainan, Sichuan); India; Nepal; Thailand; Vietnam; Laos; Indonesia.

***Tambana subflava* (Wileman, 1911) (Newly recorded for Xizang)**

Tambana subflava Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015, Zootaxa 4048 (3): 304(list). TL: China (Taiwan), Rantaizan.

Material examined: 1♂, Hanmi Township, Médog, Linzhi, XZ, 29-VII-2013, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♂, Hanmi Township, Médog, Linzhi, XZ, 18-19-VII-2021, leg. Zhaohui Pan, Enyong Chen & Yuheng Jiang. 1♂, Beibeng Township, Médog, Linzhi, XZ, 14-V-2023, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♂, 80K, Médog, Linzhi, XZ, 4-IX-2023, leg. Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. *T. subflava* medium-sized and easily distinguishable from other species of the genus *Tambana*. Head and thorax white, antennae base white. Forewings with leopard-like markings; a white spot extending from the reniform stigma to the postmedial line, reaching the costa. Hindwings yellow, only cilia tinged brown. Tegumen broad, with mountain-shaped protrusions on both sides. Cornuti on the vesica sparse and short.

Description. Male adult (Fig. 3). Forewing length 55–58 mm. Head white. Antennae filiform, base white, remaining part brown. Labial palpi short, white. Thorax patagia white, middle with one short brown line, tegulae brown and white, white ventrally. Abdomen blackish-gray, both sides with yellow scales. Anal tuft greyish-brown. Forewings ground color brown, irregularly covered with white spots. Basal and antemedial lines double blackish-brown lines, white between them. Wedge-shaped stripe blackish-brown, pointed end extending outward. Orbicular and reniform stigma white and outlined with blackish-brown. Median and Postmedial lines blackish-brown, wavy-curved, with white spots on both sides of the median line at the costal margin. Median and postmedial lines with two white spots near the reniform stigma. Subterminal line blackish-brown, wavy and curved, outer side with slight white spots. Cilia brown. Hindwings yellow, outer marginal area brown.

Male genitalia (Figs 12, 13). Uncus short and thick blunt apically. Tegumen broad with mountain-shaped protrusions on both sides. Juxta shield-shaped. Saccus long. Valvae thick, curved and lamellate. Harpe curved finger-shaped at sacculus processes. Aedeagus curved, cylindrical, with the carina plate bearing short spiniform protuberances. Vesica, with mucronate cornuti in the middle.

Distribution. China (Xizang, Jiangxi, Fujian, Guangdong, Sichuan, Yunnan, Taiwan); Nepal; India; Vietnam; Thailand.

***Tambana arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998 (Newly recorded for Xizang)**

Tambana arctoides Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015, Zootaxa 4048 (3): 306, 304(list). TL: Vietnam, Mt. Fan-si-Pan, Cha-Pa, 1500–1800 m, 22°20'N, 103°40'E.

Material examined: 1♂, Hanmi Township, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 29-VII-2013, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♀, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 25-VII-2015, leg. Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. This species is similar in appearance to *T. variegata*, but differs distinctly by its larger size and forewings tinged reddish-brown, with two white spots at the apex and base of the reniform stigma. Harpe more slender and acute than those of other species, curved in an arc. Cornuti thick and long. It has a distinct triangular antrum (prebursal sclerite). Ductus bursae short, ribbed, sclerotized at the junction with cervix bursae, cervix bursae elongate, sclerotized.

Description. Female and male adult (Figs 4, 5). Forewing length 53–62 mm. Head dark reddish brown. Antennae filiform. Labial palpi short, apically white. Thorax reddish-brown, patagia and tegulae outlined with white and greyish-white ventrally. Abdomen reddish-brown, both sides with yellow scales. Forewings ground color reddish-brown, irregularly covered with white spots. Basal and antemedial lines black, wavy-curved, with one small white patch between them. Orbicular and reniform stigma reddish-brown and outlined with black. Reniform stigma with white spots at upper and lower ends. Median and postmedial lines black, wavy-curved. Postmedial line with a white spot at the costal margin. Subterminal line brown. Cilia reddish-brown Hindwings yellow, with outer and inner margin reddish-brown.

Male genitalia (Figs 14, 15). Uncus strip-shaped, acute apically. Tegumen broad with papillate protrusions on both sides. Juxta shield-shaped. Saccus broad. Valvae thick, curved and lamellate. Harpe slender curved apically acute at sacculus processes. Aedeagus thick cylindrical, with the carina plate bearing short spiniform protuberances. Vesica membranous, with a distinct diverticulum, short cornuti formed near the apex, long spiniform cornuti formed at the apex.

Female genitalia (Fig. 21). Papillae anales cylindrical. Apophyses anterioris and apophyses posterioris equal in length, both sclerotized. Ductus bursae short and thick, with a funnel-shaped antrum and a short membranous anterior section. Corpus bursae strongly elongated and membranous, with an irregularly shaped posterior section (bilaterally protruding and relatively sclerotized), and a tubular anterior section.

Distribution. China (Xizang, Shaanxi, Sichuan); Vietnam; Myanmar.

***Tambana indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015**

Tambana indeterminata Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015, Zootaxa 4048 (3): 323, 305 (list). TL: India, Arunachal-Pradesh, road Dirang Bomdila, 2450m, 27°266'N, 92°427'E.

Material examined: 3♂, Hanmi Township, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 18-19-VII-2021, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♂, Beibeng Township, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 12-VI-2017, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♀, 2♂, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 30-VII-2016, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 8♂, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 25-VII-2015, leg. Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. This species relatively small in size, head and thorax white, forewings with metallic sheen, each line distinct, curved in a wavy manner. Hindwings base yellow, with a broad blackish-brown band presented at the outer margin. Uncus slender strip-shaped, harpe short, finger-shaped, acute distally. Cornuti sparse at base, dense at apex. Corpus bursae circular. Anterior part membranous, sclerotized, posterior part sclerotized.

Description. Male adult (Fig. 3). Forewing length 36-43 mm. Head white. Antennae filiform. Labial palpi black with white distally. Thorax white dorsally and ventrally, tegulae black. Abdomen blackish-grey. Forewings ground color dark yellowish-brown with metallic luster. Basal line short black and tinged with white exteriorly. Antemedial line black, wavy-curved, and tinged with white interiorly. Orbicular stigma white and outlined with black. Reniform stigma yellowish-brown, with a larger white patch extending to the costal margin. Postmedial line black, wavy - curved, and tinged with white exteriorly. Formation of black plaques between M₁ and M₂. Subterminal line greyish-white, marked wavy curvature, and tinged with yellowish-gray exteriorly. Cilia blackish-brown. Hindwings base yellow, with a broad blackish-brown band presented at the outer margin. Discal spot greyish-brown visible Cilia alternating greyish-brown and white.

Male genitalia (Figs 16, 17). Uncus slender strip-shaped. Tegumen broad with papillate protrusions on both sides. Juxta lamellate. Saccus broad. Valvae thick and broad. Harpe short, finger-shaped, acute distally. Aedeagus thick cylindrical. Vesica membranous, with a distinct diverticulum, cornuti sparse at base, dense at apex.

Female genitalia (Fig. 22). Papillae anales hoof-shaped. Anterior and posterior apophyses equal in length, both sclerotized. Ductus bursae short, with a funnel-shaped antrum and a short membranous anterior section. Corpus bursae circular. Anterior part membranous, sclerotized, posterior part sclerotized,

Distribution. China (Xizang, Yunnan); India; Thailand.

***Tambana variegata* Moore, 1882**

Tambana variegata Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015, Zootaxa 4048 (3): 312, 304 (list). TL: India, Prov. W Bengal, Darjeeling.

Material examined: 1♀, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 29-VII-2016, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 2♂, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 25-VII-2015, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 2♂, 80K, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 28-VII-2018, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 1♂, Beibeng Township, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 17-V-2023, leg. Zhaohui Pan. 2♂, Beibeng Township, Mêdog, Linzhi, XZ, 6-VII-2017, leg. Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. *T. variegata* resembling *T. arctoides*, but differing in wing pattern formed by thin, broken white crosslines and white suffusion. Heavy dusting of white scales between crosslines on forewing and in dark terminal field. Hindwing yellow, with diffused terminal band. Uncus broad and strip - shaped. Harpe similar to that of *T. arctoides*. Aedeagus with a distinct diverticulum, cornuti dense at apex.

Description. Female and male adult (Figs 8, 9). Forewing length 54–62 mm. Head brown tinged with white. Antennae filiform with white base. Labial palpi short, overall black, white distally. Thorax brown tinged with white. Abdomen blackish-brown, both sides with yellow scales. Forewings ground color brown with bluish-white tinge.

FIGURES 1–9. *Tambana* spp., adults. 1 ♀, *T. albiplaga* (Warren, 1912) 2 ♂, *T. entoxantha* (Hampson, 1894) 3 ♂, *T. subflava* (Wileman, 1911) 4 ♂, *T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998 5 ♀, *T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998 6 ♂, *T. indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015 7 ♀, *T. indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015 8 ♂, *T. variegata* Moore, 1882 9 ♀, *T. variegata* Moore, 1882. Scale bars: 1–9 = 1 cm.

FIGURES 10–19. *Tambana* spp., male genitalia: **10, 11** *T. entoxantha* (Hampson, 1894) **12, 13** *T. subflava* (Wileman, 1911) **14, 15** *T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998 **16, 17** *T. indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015 **18, 19** *T. variegata* Moore, 1882. Scale bars: 10–19 = 1 mm.

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22

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FIGURES 20–23. *Tambana* spp., female genitalia: **20** *T. albiplaga* (Warren, 1912) **21** *T. arctoides* Speidel & Kononenko, 1998 **22** *T. indeterminata* Behounek, Han & Kononenko, 2015 **23** *T. variegata* Moore, 1882. Scale bars: 20–23 = 1 mm.

Basal line, antemedial line, median line, postmedial line and subterminal line all black, a small white spot between basal and antemedial lines. Orbicular stigma a small white spot. Reniform stigma indistinct, with a white spot above and below respectively. Cilia brown. Hindwing yellow, with a brown terminal band.

Male genitalia (Figs 18, 19). Uncus broad band-shaped, blunt apically. Tegumen broad without protrusion. Juxta shield-shaped. Saccus long. Valvae thick, curved and lamellate. Harpe slender curved apically acute at sacculus processes. Aedeagus cylindrical, with a lamellate carina plate. Vesica membranous, with a distinct diverticulum, cornuti dense at apex.

Female genitalia (Fig. 23). Papillae anales trapezoid. Apophyses anterioris and apophyses posterioris equal in length, both sclerotized. apophyses posterioris with relatively broad shape. Ostium bursae elliptical. Ductus bursae short and broad. Corpus bursae broadly elongate-elliptical. with a sclerotized posterior section and a membranous anterior section.

Distribution. China (Xizang); India, Bhutan; Nepal; Thailand; Vietnam.

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● Additional information

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